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Impact Factor: 0.98

A STUDY OF UNIT LINKED INSURANCE PLANS IN INDIAN LIFE INSURANCE AND IMPACT OF NEW GUIDELINES FOR ULIPs IN LIFE INSURANCE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

ULIP came into play in the 1960s and is popular in many countries in the world. Unit Linked guidelines were notified by Insurance Regulatory Development Authority (IRDA) on 21st December 2005. On April 9, 2010 SEBI barred 14 life insurance companies from selling or renewing ULIPs unless they registered with it. These ULIPs had already got the approval from IRDA which led to a legal tussle between two regulators. Finally on June 18 2011, in an amendment favoring IRDA over SEBI an act was signed by Former President Pratibha Patil. The main intent of the guidelines was to ensure that they lead to greater transparency and understanding of these products among the insured, especially since the investment risk is borne by the policyholder. This study aims to analyze the recent changes made by IRDA regarding ULIPs and the impact of new guidelines for ULIPs in Indian life insurance sector.

Keywords: Growth of ULIPS, Indian Life Insurance Sector, Impact of New Guidelines for ULIPs.

INTRODUCTION

The first ULIP was launched in India in 1971 by Unit Trust of India. UTI offered the ULIP Where one small part of the premium was used as life cover and the balance was invested in units. With the Government of India opening up the insurance sector to foreign investors in 2001 and the subsequent issue of major guidelines for ULIPs by the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority of India (IRDA of India) in 2005, several insurance companies forayed into the ULIP business leading to an over abundance of ULIP schemes being launched to serve the investment needs of those looking to invest in an investment cum insurance product.

A ULIP is a life insurance policy which provides a combination of risk cover and investment. The dynamics of the capital market have a direct bearing on the performance of the ULIPs. In a ULIP, the investment risk is generally borne by the policy holder. The three important things to remember about a ULIP is that entry costs are high and the brokerage, commission could be as high as 30 percent of the premium in the first year. The second thing to remember is that management fee is low in a ULIP at around. The price of an insurance cover is higher in a ULIP than in a plain vanilla insurance policy. To that extent if a person has the time and inclination to research, he would be better off buying separate insurance and mutual funds. The third point that one must keep in mind is that in India one gets tax benefits on investing in ULIPs. As ULIPs are an efficient tax saving instrument too. The tax benefits that one can avail in case he invests in ULIPs are described below:

1. Life insurance plans are eligible for deduction under Sec. 80C.

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2. Pension plans are eligible for a deduction under Sec. 80CCC.
3. Health insurance plans and critical illness riders are eligible for deduction under Sec. 80D.

The maturity proceeds or withdrawals of life insurance policies are exempt under Sec 10(10D), subject to norms prescribed in that section.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To understand the structure of ULIPs
- To know the recent changes made by IRDA regarding ULIPs
- To Analyze the impact of new guidelines for ULIPs in Indian life insurance sector

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Data and information for the research study were collected and analyzed from secondary published sources viz., books, newspapers, and websites and research studies.

WORKING PRINCIPLE OF ULIPS

ULIP is an abbreviation for Unit Linked Insurance Policy which is a combination of life insurance and a market linked investment product. Therefore, it provides policy holders life cover as well as capital appreciation. A part of the premium paid is utilized to provide insurance cover to the policy holder while the remaining portion is invested in various equity and debt schemes. The money collected by the insurance provider is utilized to form a pool of fund that is used to invest in various markets instruments (debt and equity) in varying proportions just the way it is done for mutual funds. Policy holders have the option of selecting the type of funds (debt or equity) or a mix of both based on their investment need and appetite. Just the way it is for mutual funds, ULIP policy holders are also allotted units and each unit has a net asset value (NAV) that is declared on a daily basis. The NAV is the value based on which the net rate of returns on ULIPs are determined. The NAV varies from one ULIP to another based on market conditions and the fund's performance.

In a Unit Linked Plan (ULIP), the premiums you pay are invested in the funds chosen by you after deducting allocation charges and charges including those for managing funds, policy administration and for providing insurance cover are deducted from the funds by cancelling certain units.

TYPES OF FUNDS AVAILABLE AND THEIR RISK CHARACTERISTICS

Sl.No	General Description	Nature of Investments	Risk Category
1.	Equity Funds	Primarily invested in company stocks with the general aim of capital appreciation.	Medium to High
2.	Income, Fixed Interest and Bond Funds	Invested in corporate bonds, government securities and other fixed income instruments.	Medium
3.	Cash Funds	Sometimes known as Money Market Funds- invested in cash, bank deposits and money market instruments.	Low
4.	Balanced Funds	Combining equity investment with fixed interest instruments.	Medium

The value of each unit of a fund is determined by dividing the total value of the fund's investments by the total number of units.

CHARGES

a) Administration charges: A fee is charged for administration of your policy every month. Administration charges are deducted by cancelling units proportionately from each of the funds you have chosen.

b) Fund management charges: These charges are towards meeting expenses related to managing the fund. This is charged as a percentage of the fund's value and is deducted before arriving at the net asset value of the fund.

c) Switch charges: Policyholders' can switch between the funds available to suit Policyholders' changing needs and goals. In a policy year, a fixed number of such switches are available free of cost. Subsequent to this, each switch would attract a certain charge. These charges are deducted by cancelling units proportionately from each of the funds you have chosen.

d) Surrender charges: These charges are levied for premature encashment of units. They are charged as a percentage of the fund value and depend on the policy year in which the policy has been surrendered.

e) Mortality Charges: Depending upon the age, and the amount of cover, these charges are levied towards providing a death cover to the insured.

f) Premium Allocation Charge: This charge is deducted as a fixed percentage of the premium received, and is usually charged at a higher rate in the initial years of a policy. This charge varies depending upon whether the policy is a single premium or regular premium policy, the size of the premium, premium frequency and payment mode.

g) Partial Withdrawal Charges: Lump sum withdrawals are allowed from the fund after the lapse of three years of the policy term and subject to pre- specified conditions. However, such withdrawals attract charges, as mentioned in the respective policy brochures.

h) Free Look Period: As per IRDA of India, the policyholder can seek refund of premiums if he disagrees with the terms and conditions of the policy, within 15 days of receipt of the policy document (Free Look period). The policyholder shall be refunded the fund value including charges levied through cancellation of units subject to deduction of expenses towards medical examination, stamp duty and proportionate risk premium for the period of cover.

ULIPs Controversies

It is estimated that Investors lost Rs.1.5 trillion due to insurance mis-selling. Most news papers in India covered various stories and critically reviewed these insurance institutions which mis-sold these ULIPS to the small investors. Mint newspaper famously quoted it as "The ULIP rip-off was an institutional defrauding of the small investors" and covered it in an article ULIP Rips off Consumers. Capital mind, an excellent investor caring news outfit covered it as early as 2007 to educate consumers on how not to get defrauded by these ULIP schemes. Public interest litigation was filed as well while hundreds of thousands of small investors lost their hard earned money, some even committing suicides, the agents enjoyed their commissions and the executives of these insurance companies collected Crores in bonuses by mis-selling these ULIPS.

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Unit Linked guidelines were notified by Insurance Regulatory Development Authority of India on 21st December 2005. On April 9, 2010 SEBI barred 14 life insurance companies from selling or renewing ULIPs unless they registered with it. These ULIPs had already got the approval from IRDA of India which led to a legal tussle between two regulators. Finally on June 18 2011, in an amendment favoring IRDA of India over SEBI an act was signed by President Pratibha Patil. The main intent of the guidelines was to ensure that they lead to greater transparency and understanding of these products among the insured, especially since the investment risk is borne by the policyholder.

CHANGES MADE BY IRDA REGARDING ULIPS

I. DISTRIBUTION CHANNEL RELATED CHANGES

- (1). IRDA has amended the IRDA of India (**Insurance Advertisements and Disclosure**) Regulations to remove any scope for the involvement of unlicensed personnel/entities in the sale of insurance products.
- (2). IRDA has amended the IRDA of India (**Licensing of Corporate Agents**) Regulations to further tighten the Code of Conduct of corporate agents to ensure that the prospect does not deal with any unlicensed person. The Regulations have also been amended to ensure that there is no scope for any kind of remuneration other than commission where sale has been affected. This measure will reduce the expenses of the insurer, thereby lowering premiums to be paid by the policyholder.
- (3). Regulations for referrals: IRDA of India has also addressed the issue of Referrals by bringing out separate Regulations leaving no scope for misuse of the system. Companies which wish to share their database of customers with insurers would need to get approval from IRDA of India after having conformed to the requirements as laid down in the Regulations. Further, there are restrictions on the business activities of the referral company to ensure that there is no misuse of the system.

II. ULIP STRUCTURE RELATED CHANGES

- (1). **Lock in period increased to five years:** IRDA has increased the lock-in period for all Unit Linked Products from three years to five years, including top-up premiums, thereby making them long term financial instruments which basically provide risk protection.
- (2). **Level Paying Premiums:** Further, all regular premium /limited premium ULIPs shall have uniform/level paying premiums. Any additional payments shall be treated as single premium for the purpose of insurance cover.
- (3). **Even Distribution of Charges:** Charges on ULIPs are mandated to be evenly distributed during the lock in period, to ensure that high front ending of expenses is eliminated.
- (4). **Minimum Premium Paying Term Of Five Years:** All limited premium unit linked insurance products, other than single premium products shall have premium paying term of at least five years.
- (5). **Increase In Risk Component:** Further, all unit linked products, other than pension and annuity products shall provide a mortality cover or a health cover thereby increasing the risk cover component in such products.
 - (i) The minimum mortality cover should be as follows:

Minimum Sum assured for age at entry of below 45 years	Minimum Sum assured for age at entry of 45 years and above
Single Premium (SP) contracts: 125 percent of single premium.	Single Premium (SP) contracts: 110 percent of single premium
Regular Premium (RP) including limited premium paying (LPP) contracts: 10 times the annualized premiums or (0.5 X T X annualized premium) whichever is higher. At no time the death benefit shall be less than 105 percent of the total premiums (including top-ups) paid.	Regular Premium (RP) including limited premium paying (LPP) contracts: 7 times the annualized premiums or (0.25 X T X annualized premium) whichever is higher. At no time the death benefit shall be less than 105 percent of the total premiums (including top-ups) paid.

SOURCE: IRDA of India

(In case of whole life contracts, term (T) shall be taken as 70 minus age at entry)

(ii) The minimum health cover per annum should be as follows:

Minimum annual health cover for age at entry of below 45 years	Minimum annual health cover for age at entry of 45 years and above
Regular Premium (RP) contracts: 5 times the annualized premiums or Rs. 100,000 per annum whichever is higher, At no time the annual health cover shall be less than 105 percent of the total premiums paid.	Regular Premium (RP) contracts: 5 times the annualized premiums or Rs. 75,000 per annum whichever is higher. At no time the annual health cover shall be less than 105 percent of the total premiums paid

SOURCE: IRDA of India

(6). Minimum Guaranteed Return for Pension Products: As regards pension products, all ULIP pension/annuity products shall offer a minimum guaranteed return of 4.5% per annum or as specified by IRDA of India from time to time. This will protect the life time savings for the pensioners, from any adverse fluctuations at the time of maturity.

(7). Rationalization of cap on charges: With a view to smoothening the cap on charges, the capping been rationalized to ensure that the difference in yield is capped from the 5th year onwards. This will not only reduce the overall charges on these products, but also smoothen the charge structure for the policyholder.

III. DISCONTINUANCE OF CHARGES

IRDA of India has also addressed the issue of discontinuance of charges for surrender of ULIPs. The IRDA of India (Treatment of Discontinued Linked Insurance Policies) Regulations brought out by IRDA of India in this regard ensure that policyholders do not get overcharged when they wish to discontinue their policies for any emergency cash requirement. The Regulations stipulate that an insurer shall recover only the incurred acquisition costs in the event of discontinuance of policy and that these charges are not excessive. The discontinuance charges have been capped both as percentage of fund value and premium and also in absolute value. The Regulations also clearly define the Grace Period for different modes of premium payment. Upon discontinuance of a policy, a policyholder shall be entitled to exercise an option of either reviving the policy or completely withdrawing from the policy without any risk cover. Further, the regulations also enable IRDA of India to order refund of discontinuance charges in case they are found excessive on enquiry.

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These regulations are applicable to all new ULIP products approved by IRDA of India after these regulations are notified and these regulations changed the face of the ULIP insurance market and IRDA of India has now formulated a new set of regulations for Non Linked Insurance Plans.

IMPACT OF NEW GUIDELINES FOR ULIPS

- Profitability of insurance companies will be impacted with its new guidelines for unit-linked plans, which invest part of funds in equities. The regulator advised the insurance companies to reduce their expenses to maintain the bottom line in the long run.
- Capping of surrender charges and the even distribution of charges over the lock-in period of five years will adversely impact the profitability of companies. So there will be an impact (on profitability). Ultimately the idea of guidelines is to have impact. IRDA of India's concern for the insurance industry is not what is going to happen in 2015-16. The concern is that the industry must remain healthy, be able to grow and be sustainable.
- ULIP sales will also be adversely affected as agents may be unwilling to sell products at lower commissions.
- Also new ULIP pension plans at a minimum guaranteed return of 4.5% p.a. have not been launched by most life insurers after September 2010 as both companies & policyholders have found them unattractive.
- It is clear that the unit linked guidelines have significantly contributed to the decline in new business premium collections during October 2010 to September 2011. However, we also need to bear in mind the context of the prevailing economic conditions since the global financial crisis in 2008/09 that could have also contributed to the declining proportion of linked business. From its peak contribution to total individual new business premium of 86% during the fiscal year ending 31 March 2008, the contribution of unit linked business steadily declined to 60% in the fiscal year ending 31 March 2011.
- As noted earlier, the biggest casualty of the ULIP guidelines has been the individual life unit linked pensions business, which recorded a decline of close to 96% during the period October 2010 to September 2011, on a year-on-year basis.
- The insurance companies must take a look at long term achievements and should bear with the initial hiccups. Because "Insurance is always a long term industry. What might happen in six months and one year is not important. There may be some hiccups. What is going to happen in mid- and long-term is significant. So what might happen in the given year is not important.
- The insurance companies can go for cost-cutting measures in order to maintain the profitability. The company may try to contain cost by electricity bills, administrative cost, travel cost and also agents cost. There will be a host of things to be implemented. The insurance companies should redesign their products and they must be in the interest of policy holders.

GROWTH OF ULIPS (Premium wise)

LINKED PREMIUM OF LIFE INSURERS FOR 2012-13 (Premium in Rs.Crore)

	Regular	Single	First Year	Renewal	Total
PRIVATE TOTAL	8225.27	2398.06	10623.33	31621.87	42245.20
LIC	40.13	151.83	191.96	6338.40	6530.35
GRAND TOTAL	8265.39	2549.89	10815.29	37960.27	48775.55

SOURCE: IRDA of India Annual Report 2013 - 2014

LINKED PREMIUM OF LIFE INSURERS FOR 2013-14 (Premium in Rs.Crore)

	Regular	Single	First Year	Renewal	Total
PRIVATE TOTAL	6926.88	1637.95	8564.83	26253.94	34818.76
LIC	9.10	34.75	43.85	2684.40	2728.25
GRAND TOTAL	6935.98	1672.70	8608.68	28938.33	37547.01

SOURCE: IRDA of India Annual Report 2013 - 2014

CONCLUSION

ULIP guidelines were first introduced in December 2005 and the first set of major changes to these guidelines were issued in 2009, when the Insurance Regulatory and Development Authority (IRDA of India) mandated a cap on charges on Unit Linked Insurance plans. This set in motion a massive industry-wide exercise of repricing the unit linked products and introducing initiatives to control costs.

It was the ban on sale of ULIPs by the Securities and Exchange Board of India (SEBI) on the grounds that they had not been approved by SEBI that resulted in the sweeping changes introduced by IRDA of India by way of the revised unit linked guidelines, which came into effect from 1 September 2010 (ULIP guidelines). The industry reacted to these changes through further control on costs, overhauling their product strategy, revisiting their profit margins, making changes in their distribution strategy and, in some cases, conducting a complete and/or radical rethink of strategy and operations. On top of the ULIP guidelines, IRDA of India issued additional guidelines in 2011 that led to a further tightening of norms for all forms of insurance intermediation, including agents, corporate agents, referral arrangements and distance marketing.

Those who are basing their decision not to invest in Unit Linked Insurance Plan are considering the 2010 scenario when this was not something, which seemed glamorous and worthwhile by any standards. Today, however the situation has changed much especially in view of recent IRDA of India amendments. This ensures higher protection for the consumers. In order to do away with the misleading view that ULIP is a short-term plan, IRDA of India has increased the lock in period for this scheme, from the earlier three years to five years from now. This attracts only those investors who are after long-term gains. Those who are looking for an ideal investment vehicle for 2014 can surely opt for the Unit Linked Insurance Plan, without much speculation. People who were averse to ULIP even sometimes back are opting for it once again naturally because of the related benefits, which make it a worthwhile investment option in the current scenario.

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